

ISic3426

I.Sicily inscription 3426

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication (?)

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.03.28

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Euryelos, from the 'Dionysian walls', from the slope below the fortifications by the city gate crossed by the modern 'via Epipole', in the direction of the castello Eurialo

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Area archeologica Castello Eurialo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644821

Bibliography

Gentili, G.V. 1961. Nuovi elementi di epigrafia siracusana. *Archivio Storico Siracusano*. 7: 5-25. At 6-7 no.1 ph dr

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3426. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388554>